

Temple 2048 of Tell el-Mutesellum/Megiddo

Data source: Godscapes project

By Gaia Cecconi, University La Sapienza

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Levantine Religion, Sacred Enclosure, Ritual Deposit, Middle Bronze Age, Southern Levant, Southern Levant, Canaanite Religions, Temple, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult in southern Levant, Ritual centre

Temple 2048 was located in the north-eastern sector of the upper mound of Tell el-Mutesellim/Megiddo and it was excavated by the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, under the direction of G. Loud during '30s and by the Tel Aviv University since 1992. This temple has been built in a area where it is testified the continued establishment of temples and sacred open areas since Early Bronze Age I, proving that the local population had assigned to this area a strong sacred value. The architectural evolution of Temple 2048 has been divided into three phases by G. Loud (Strata VIII-VIIB-A), who dated the first two stages to Late Bronze Age II and the third one to Iron Age I. Although, successive studies and comparisons, especially with the Strata XVI-XV temple of Tell Balata/Shechem, reconducted this temple to the well-known type of MB III temples called "Migdol temple". Recent analysis of the architectural evolution of Temple 2048 and the buildings around (Cecconi in press) individuated four architectural phases. Temple 2048 has a south-west/north-east orientation, and it was built during Middle Bronze Age III/Late Bronze Age on an artificially raised platform. The temple, measuring 21.5 x 16.5 m, is made up of a single long room of 11.5x9.6 m, with massive walls built with two external block facades and a small rubble filling. The façade features two towers of varying sizes on each side: the eastern tower is larger than the western one, most likely due to the presence of a staircase. A niche was built at the center of the back wall of the temple, on a direct axis with the entrance. The temple was rebuilt in the second phase (Late Bronze Age I-II) using an "ashlar stones" technique: the eastern tower was repaired and two columns were added at the outer entrance. In the third phase, dated to Late Bronze Age II, the inner niche was closed, and a platform was built in place of the external niche, modification celebrated by the deposition in this room of three hoards. The façade is distinguished in this phase by the proximity of the western tower to a casemate temenos wall that surrounded and delimited the sacred space around the temple. In the last phase, dated to the Iron Age I-II, the temple was rebuilt with considerable changes: from smaller dimensions to the appearance of both a niche and a platform, to the transformation of the towers of the entrance-hall into two cells and the removal of the previous casemate wall. Temple 2048 is characterized by a bounding around of subsidiary buildings, that separate the temple from the urban layout. The function of these buildings is not clear: the findings testify a connection with the temple, and the presence of a high level social group, that was involved in the sacred ceremonies and in the local bureaucracy. This temple belongs to the urban "Migdol Temples" group (Susnow M., 2021, *The Practice of Canaanite Cult. The Middle and Late Bronze Ages*), an architectural typology well known in the Middle Bronze Age III-Late Bronze Southern Levant, at Hazor (Area H Temple), Tell Balata/Sichem and Pella. This temple is distinguished by specific criteria (Mazar A., 1992, *Temples of the Middle and Late Bronze Age and the Iron Age*, pp. 161-187 in *The Architecture of Ancient Israel from the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*) involving most of their outside appearance, while the inner layout is highly varying. Important features of this model are the monumentality, dictated by the massive walls and the two towers on the façade, and the worship of a male deity (Ba'al or Reshef). These features are strictly associated to a visible rule by a local elite, whose central building was frequently the only one connected to the sacred region.

Date Range: 1650 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: Megiddo

Region tags: Israel, Middle East

Megiddo in the southern Levant

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Platform

Notes: The temple was constructed on an artificially raised platform, described as a series of rubble layers (not less than eight), of about 20/30 cm of thickness, that in some places extended beyond the outer wall face

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The temple, measuring 21.5 x 16.5 m, is made up of a single long room of 11.5x9.6 m, with massive walls built with two external block facades and a small rubble filling. The façade features two towers of varying sizes on each side: the eastern tower is larger than

the western one, most likely due to the presence of a staircase. A niche was built at the center of the back wall of the temple, on a direct axis with the entrance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Around the temples a series of bordering buildings and walls are attested, in order to delimitate the sacred space of the temples and the courtyard around it. The function of these buildings is still unclear: the materials indicate clearly a connection with the temple but don't specify the activities that were carried on inside these buildings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ A group of features:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Temple 2048 stands in an area where other temples had been built in Early Bronze and a sacred open area in Middle Bronze I-II

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Worship:**

–Other [specify]: Communal worship, but ruled over by a small group

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Is the structure/feature finished:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Was the structure/feature modified through time:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Was the structure/feature destroyed:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **In antiquity**

– Periodically

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ba'al/Reshef

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Loud, G. *Megiddo II: Seasons of 1935–39* (Oriental Institute Publications 62), Chicago: University of Chicago Press 1948.

– Source 2: Dunayevsky, I. – Kempinski, A. *The Megiddo Temples: Zeitschrift des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins* 89 (1973), pp. 161–87.

– Source 3: Epstein, C. *An Interpretation of the Megiddo Sacred Area During the Middle Bronze II: Israel Exploration Journal* 15 (1965), pp. 204–221.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Notes: Temple 2048 was built in the same place as other temples/open areas that had already been established and was decommissioned. The region where the platform was created, in particular, has been raised from the prior lower level of the old Open region (Middle Bronze Age I-II), which corresponded to the urban center's walking level.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Type of feature

- Mound
- Clearing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

- Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/publications/oip/oip-62-megiddo-2-seasons-1935%E2%80%931939-text-and-plates>
- Source 1 Description: Website where it is possible to download the volumes Megiddo II, there Temple 2048 has been described

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Type of excavation:

- Pre-modern

Notes: Excavations by the University of Chicago during years 1935-1939, under the direction of G. Loud.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

— Scientific

Notes: Excavations by the Hebrew University during the '60s, under the direction of I. Dunayevsky, and A. Kempinski

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Years of excavation:

— Year range: 1935-1939

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

— Year range: 1960-1968

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Name of excavation

— Official or descriptive name: Excavations by the Hebrew University, under the direction of I. Dunayevsky, and A. Kempinski

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

— Official or descriptive name: Excavations by the University of Chicago, under the direction of G. Loud.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

— Yes

Notes: Temple 2048 is characterized by a temenos composed by subsidiary buildings that divided the sacred area from the rest of the urban layout.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Temple 2048 has been built in the same area where the previous temples of Early and Middle Bronze Age I-II have been established and dismissed. Throughout its existence, this temple was flanked and linked by the Palace of Nordburg.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: Elite

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

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Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion toward a male deity

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Sources and Excavations

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

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Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Platform

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Type of feature

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Region: Levant

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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Region: Levant

↳ A single structure

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Specific to this answer:

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↳ A group of structures:

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Notes: Around the temples a series of bordering buildings and walls are attested, in order to delimitate the sacred space of the temples and the courtyard around it. The function of these buildings is still unclear: the materials indicate clearly a connection with the temple but don't specify the activities that were carried on inside these buildings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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– Yes

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Notes: Temple 2048 stands in an area where other temples had been built in Early Bronze and a sacred open area in Middle Bronze I-II

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Communal worship, but ruled over by a small group

Specific to this answer:

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– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ba'al/Reshef

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: Elite

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Region: Levant

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– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion toward a male deity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Humans**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Supernatural narratives**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Human narratives**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **Other [Specify]**

– Other [specify]: The materials, in particular the presence of weapons and bronze statues from the foundation deposit, indicates the presence of a worship for a male deity (Ba'al or Reshef)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The monumentality is a characteristic of the migdol temples, the architectural typology to which Temple 2048 belongs, and it is composed by the presence of huge perimetral walls and two towers on the facade.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ **In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:**

– Percentage: 60

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 355

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Earth

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Clay

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Plaster

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Wood

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The monumentality is a characteristic of the migdol temples, the architectural typology to which Temple 2048 belongs, and it is composed by the presence of huge perimetral walls and two tower on the facade.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 355

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Region: Levant

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– Field doesn't know

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Region: Levant

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Earth

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Eyes (stylized or not)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

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Specific to this answer:

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– Field doesn't know

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– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

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– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Humans

– Field doesn't know

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Region: Levant

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The materials, in particular the presence of weapons and bronze statues from the foundation deposit, indicates the presence of a worship for a male deity (Ba'al or Reshef)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals and ceremony took place inside the temple, and maybe processions had also placed outside in the courtyard. The size of these rituals can be considered small because the dimensions of the temple allow just a small percentage of the population to get inside the sacred building, on the opposite to the previous Open Area of the Middle Bronze Age I-II, when all the population could see and have access to the sacred elements.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Migdol temples don't show the chance to practice large-scale rituals inside them

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Most of the offerings belongs to the last two phases of the temple (Late Bronze and Iron Age). There have been found five hoards inside the cella, composed by metallic times and fragments of Egyptian statues

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Other

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Few burials have been found in the Eastern Sector of the buildings around the sacred area around Temple 2048

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ As cenotaphs:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In cemetery:

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Region: Levant

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Region: Levant

Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Other

– Other [specify]: Few burials have been found in the Eastern Sector of the buildings around the sacred area around Temple 2048

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals and ceremony took place inside the temple, and maybe processions had also placed outside in the courtyard. The size of these rituals can be considered small because the dimensions of the temple allow just a small percentage of the population to get inside the sacred building, on the opposite to the previous Open Area of the Middle Bronze Age I-II, when all the population could see and have access to the sacred elements.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Migdol temples don't show the chance to practice large-scale rituals inside them

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

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Region: Levant

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Most of the offerings belongs to the last two phases of the temple (Late Bronze and Iron Age). There have been found five hoards inside the cella, composed by metallic times and fragments of Egyptian statues

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The typology of urban migdol temples indicates a control by the socio-political elite ruling the community where the temple has been built

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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Region: Levant

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Bureaucracy

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Specific to this answer:

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Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Temple 2048 of Tell el-Mutesellum/Megiddo, Loud, G.. *Megiddo II: Seasons of 1935-39*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1948.

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